

Business Plan

Deliverable D1.3

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

This deliverable discusses options and plans for transferring the ESIWACE activity into sustainable services for the community. ESIWACE consists of two kinds of activities: explicit and specific actions, for which we have milestones and deliverables, and a more implicit set of activities which revolve around collaboration and setting and achieving shared objectives. Key to both sorts of activities is the set of stakeholders – partners in the activities and objective definition, and users, both within partner institutions and elsewhere.

2. Conclusion & Results

We expect the community to continue to advocate and work towards very high resolution cloud resolving Earth system models. ESIWACE will continue to take a lead in developing and scoping that work and ensuring that the core developments needed to take it forward are maintained with the ESIWACE framework until the time when a bigger effort can be funded. To that end, the ESIWACE focus will remain on the largest problems, those for which exascale computing is necessary, and for which entirely new paradigms of working will be necessary, including re-evaluating how we use HPC in a future world where power constraints will make our existing workflows prohibitively expensive.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
Improve the efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulation on high-performance computing platforms	Yes
Support the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modelling for weather and climate simulation in high performance computing environments	Yes
The European weather and climate science community will drive the governance structure that defines the services to be provided by ESIWACE	Yes

Foster the interaction between industry and the weather and climate community on the exploitation of high-end computing systems, application codes and services.	Yes
Increase competitiveness and growth of the European HPC industry	Yes

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Provide services to the user community that will impact beyond the lifetime of the project.	Yes
Improve scalability and shorten the time-to-solution for climate and operational weather forecasts at increased resolution and complexity to be run on future extreme-scale HPC systems.	Yes
Foster usability of the available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures.	Yes
Pursue exploitability of climate and weather model results.	Yes
Establish governance of common software management to avoid unnecessary and redundant development and to deliver the best available solutions to the user community.	Yes
Provide open access to research results and open source software at international level.	Yes
Exploit synergies with other relevant activities and projects and also with the global weather and climate community	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

The full detailed report can be found in Annex 1. The deliverable is a document in form of a white paper discussing strategies for future activities. It is the result of intense discussions of the authors with the ESIWACE partners and other stakeholders.

5. References (*Bibliography*)

See the references in the document.

6. Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

The content of this deliverable will be disseminated through workshops, newsletters and personal communications.

7. The delivery is delayed: Yes No

The delivery was originally planned for October 2018. We indicated at the review in early November 2018 that we would delay this deliverable, in order to coordinate contributions from the newly approved projects ESIWACE2, IS-ENES3, and ESCAPE-2.

8. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

For the DoA it was expected to develop two alternative strategies, one with continued EU-funding for the activities started by ESIWACE and one without such a funding.

Since the ESIWACE project was established, and this deliverable was specified in the DoA, the wider environment has changed significantly; there is now a second project supporting the development of ESIWACE (i.e. ESIWACE2), and there are a number of other relevant activities which impinge on the ESIWACE endeavour. As a consequence, a detailed business plan is no longer appropriate *at this time*. Instead the objective of this document is to discuss strategic options and concrete opportunities for long-term sustainability of services to support HPC dependent Earth system modelling in Europe. It is now a description of how we will develop a sustainability plan, and how we expect it to evolve into a business plan by the end of ESIWACE2. Of necessity it addresses some key external activities and how they impinge directly on the sustainability and ongoing economics of this centre of excellence.

Business Plan

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1 Introduction

This document discusses options and plans for transferring the ESiWACE activity into sustainable services for the community. ESiWACE consists of two kinds of activities: explicit and specific actions, for which we have milestones and deliverables, and a more implicit set of activities which revolve around collaboration and setting and achieving shared objectives. Key to both sorts of activities are the set of stakeholders – partners in the activities and objective definition, and users, both within partner institutions and elsewhere.

In the original proposal for ESiWACE we emphasized the need for sustained support of shared Earth system modelling activities, in particular models and data management, to keep them synchronized with the evolving supercomputer environment and community goals (ESiWACE proposal (2016), Mitchell et al., 2012¹). Sustainability is intimately linked to the economics of the activity, hence the need for a business plan. However, in addressing such a plan we need to address both classes of activities, the tangible products and services, and the less tangible community coordination, goal setting, and representation.

For the tangible products and services there is no direct market² today for most³ of them, in that they are used by (primarily) the weather and climate modeling community partners who are (primarily) non-profit scientific institutions. We are also committed to developing open

¹ Mitchell J., Budich R., Joussaume S., Lawrence B. and Marotzke J. (2012), Infrastructure strategy for the European Earth System Modelling community 2012-2022, ENES Report Series 1, 33pp. <https://doi.org/10.5285/ca90b281d6ff4cffb9a9bbdeb5fa63f3>

² We are defining a market here as an environment where consumers can choose from a range of suppliers and there is some element of pressure on cost from the competition between supply and demand. This is manifestly not the case in a shared activity.

³ We will see that there are some real marketable “appliances” being developed within ESiWACE2 by our industrial partners, we discuss those later.

access software and delivering open data. Where there is a real market (e.g. in numerical weather prediction and climate services), organisations develop their own business models, often based on open access to research based IPR and open data). For the less tangible activities, ESiWACE is one of a number of projects addressing the strategic goals of the community – no one project has been able to address the full range of community requirements – and it is likely that a truly long-term strategic sustainable business plan needs to address these together, regardless of their current funding and scope.

Any such plan needs to consider both concrete options for support and the wider environment. Since the ESiWACE project was established, and this deliverable was specified, the wider environment has changed significantly; there is now a second phase of ESiWACE (ESiWACE2) activity, and there are a number of other relevant activities which impinge on the ESiWACE endeavour. As a consequence, a detailed business plan is no longer appropriate *at this time*. Instead the objective of this document is to discuss strategic options and concrete opportunities for long-term sustainability of services to support HPC dependent Earth system modelling in Europe. It is now a description of how we will develop a sustainability plan, and how we expect it to evolve into a business plan by the end of ESiWACE2. Of necessity it addresses some key external activities and how they impinge directly on the sustainability and ongoing economics of this centre of excellence.

2 Scope and Outline

As originally conceived, the ESiWACE business plan would have presented two alternative concepts: one for a second funded phase of ESiWACE and one for continued engagement without further EU funding. As inputs, a number of steps were outlined in the ESiWACE proposal, we discuss those steps and their outcomes in section 3. In the meantime, the opportunity to apply for a second phase presented itself sooner than expected and a number of strategies towards sustainability of ESiWACE developments and services were included in the ESiWACE2 proposal. The project was accepted to start in January 2019 with additional partners and enhanced financial support by the EU. These aspects will be discussed in more detail in section 4.

Furthermore, the wider environment changed: existing activities have morphed, in some cases expanding, in some cases contracting; new projects have started, and new community collaborations have been established. The European HPC environment has changed, with the advent of the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking (JU) providing a sharpening of the agenda for the Centres of Excellence. We will discuss these aspects in section 5.

Finally, in section 6 we address the next steps to be taken in the closing phase of ESiWACE and how we expect the ESiWACE2 business plan to evolve in response to the results of the first ESiWACE activity and the external drivers.

3 Concrete Actions from the ESiWACE Description of the Action

A number of specific actions to evaluate options securing sustainability of the ESiWACE activities were foreseen in the ESiWACE workplan. These were:

- a. *ESiWACE private partners will investigate the possibility of providing selected components of the ESM workflow as building blocks. The increased maintainability of the ESM applications and increased efficiency of the associated workflow through commercial products (e.g. adding to established tools such as debuggers) could be beneficial not only for ESM users, but at the same time applicable to other markets and thus be rendered profitable.*

The three ESiWACE private partners, Bull/ATOS, Seagate and Arm, have investigated the possibility to provide components of the ESM workflow as building blocks. These components are targeted to increase both maintainability and efficiency. Moreover, the goal was to identify and propose solutions that could be beneficial for a wider community (not only ESM), as commercial products applicable to other HPC market segments and thus be rendered profitable.

The development of the Arm tools, guided by the requirements of the ESM community, have led to an increase in flexibility and automation within the tools. This facilitates the integration with 3rd party tools, for components such as workflow managers and continuous integration suites. These principles and capabilities added to the tools have wide implications, and are benefitting other customers, outside of the ESM community.

Seagate developed the Clovis/Object store backend for ESM within ESiWACE. ESiWACE helped to increase the outreach of Clovis/Mero Object Store into the weather and climate community and helped to further harden the Mero Object store backend. Work on the Mero Object storage backend is continuing not just in ESiWACE2 follow on, but also in other H2020 projects such as Sage2 and MAESTRO. ESiWACE has been of strategic value to Seagate in helping to understand the specific storage and data needs of the climate and weather community. Indeed it's a project that helps to support the overall landscape of object storage based solutions for HPC. ESiWACE has helped to build very valuable relationships with the leading weather and climate communities within Europe, and understand their roadmap for data and storage needs. Seagate will continue to support this process in the near term.

We work on increasing the acceptance of Clovis and Mero within the European extreme-scale computing community through ESiWACE and other actions, to ultimately have an impact on the future market.

Bull mainly contributes to ESiWACE through optimisation of the source code of NEMO. This work increases the efficiency of this application, but this is not a “building block” neither a commercial product. Nevertheless, three contributions arise from this work:

- The principles used in the optimisations can be applied to other codes, not only in the weather and climate community, which is applicable in the HPC “service” market. So, this increases our knowledge and thus our competitiveness when proposing a better offer when responding to RFP for new machines and HPC services.
- Part of the optimisation work led to envision the possibility to provide such building blocks. One example is the extension of the Bull MPI library with optimised support for domain relevant features. This represents a clear differentiator compared to competitors.
- For the ESiWACE2 project BULL co-coordinates a work package aiming at developing a prototype service activity which will offer this type of optimisation work as a service.

b. *A very concrete goal we have set in this respect is the long-term continuation of the series of annual high quality workshops on HPC. The partners will commit to organize these and funding through private partners will be secured.*

The 4th and the 5th ENES HPC workshop were organised by ESiWACE. Funding for two further workshops has been secured via ESiWACE2 (the 6th ENES HPC workshop in Hamburg, 2020) and IS-ENES-3 (the 7th workshop in Barcelona, 2022). For all past workshops we could raise substantial financial sponsoring from the private HPC sector and we are confident that the interest of the private sector to contribute to these workshops through financial contributions and active participation will continue.

c. *Commitment from the partners of ESiWACE and potentially some of the supporters to long-term support of individual software components from institutional funding. This is in their own interest, fulfilling their own needs, but also benefitting from other partners, through distributed and shared efforts (thus avoiding redundant re-development). ESiWACE, by strengthening the sharing of software development, is an important step in that direction.*

ESiWACE has put a special focus on enabling very-high-resolution simulations with established weather and climate models. These models are central pillars of the institutional strategies of the scientific partners. The improvements, implemented by ESiWACE, enhance the capability of the models and will be maintained by the model owners. The MPIM for example has a clear scientific strategy based on very-high-resolution modelling, which includes the institutional commitment to sustain the ESiWACE work on ICON.

This is manifested through the DYAMOND initiative, investigating the scientific potential and capabilities of high-resolution models in the scope of an intercomparison of models, including the ESiWACE demonstrators, but also a number of international state-of-the-art models, which has clearly demonstrated the impact of convection-resolving vs parameterised simulation configurations. Also this initiative has been supported and – on the European side – enabled by ESiWACE, it was only possible through scientific drive, commitment and significant contribution from the model owners.

NEMO (Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean) is a European Platform for Ocean Modelling. NEMO is a joined activity governed by a Consortium agreement since 2008, involving in 2019: CNRS, UK Met Office, NERC, CMCC and Mercator Ocean. The goal of the Consortium is to set up appropriate arrangements for the successful and sustainable development of the NEMO System as a well-organised, state-of-the-art ocean model code system suitable for both research and operational work, e.g. for ocean sciences, climate studies (IPCC) and operational oceanography (CMEMS). NEMO developments follow a common strategy (2018-2022)⁴ elaborated with the whole community. Activities related to HPC issues are conducted by the NEMO HPC working group. This group is open to members from institutions contributing to HPC developments such as BSC and ECMWF. Code improvements done within ESiWACE tasks will thus feedback into a code used by a much wider community.

EC-Earth is both a state-of-the-art Earth system model and a consortium that develops and applies the model. The consortium was formed in 2006 and comprises currently 33 international partners (all of them from ECMWF member states), a number which has steadily grown since 2006. Of those, 8 partners have signed a Memorandum of Understanding, which obligates to contribute financially to the consortium and entitles to have a representative in the EC-Earth Steering Group, the governing body of the EC-Earth consortium. The remaining partners have signed a Letter of Intent, in which the institutions commit themselves to actively work on the development of the EC-Earth model. All partners are entitled to technical support provided by the previously mentioned financial contributions. Furthermore, much of the work done on and with EC-Earth was (and still is) supported through several national and

⁴ <https://www.nemo-ocean.eu/consortium/governance/>

international projects, particularly within the FP7 and H2020 frameworks, in particular ESIWACE but also many others (such as THOR, IS-ENES, COMBINE, SUMO, EMBRACE, ICE2SEA, SPECS, IS-ENES2, HiResClim). Again, code improvements done within ESIWACE tasks will thus feedback into a code used by a much wider community.

The OpenIFS is the research tool of ECMWF's IFS that is available to the wider research community. OpenIFS will be integrated in the EC-Earth Earth-system model. EC-Earth is one of the leading European climate models in the Coupled Model Intercomparison Projects that lay the foundation for the IPCC assessment reports. EC-Earth also contains the NEMO ocean model. ESIWACE has enabled research on code optimisation of both IFS and NEMO towards achieving the 1-km global demonstrators in phase-1, which will be further extended in phase-2 for benchmarks on the EuroHPC HPC infrastructures. The ESIWACE work on IFS for single precision, concurrent execution of model components and programming models for overlapping communication and computation will be integrated in the operational IFS as soon as possible, and eventually be made available to the wider community via OpenIFS and EC-Earth.

At present, ECMWF is developing its new finite-volume module (FVM) based dynamical core that promises better scalability on large HPC node allocations compared to the operational spectral-transform (ST) formulation of the IFS. The FVM runs on the same grid as the ST and will be added for benchmarking once the remaining scientific developments are completed. Through the INCITE programme, ECMWF already won a dedicated allocation on the No.1 HPC Summit system (according to top500.org) for the assessment of both ST and FVM at full scale and 1-km resolution. The ST configuration was developed as one of the ESIWACE demonstrators. The results will be disseminated via ESIWACE2 and provide guidance for other modelling systems and future options in the community model EC-Earth.

Even centres that were unable to contribute to this activity with current operational models have noted the need to prepare for the opportunities afforded by exascale computing by developing programmes to build new models capable of overcoming the scalability challenges such as the LFRic project at the Met Office or the Dynamico development in France.

The OASIS coupler, developed since 1991 at CERFACS, is used today by more than 45 climate-modelling groups around the world. OASIS3-MCT is, for example, used in 5 of the 7 European ESMs that participate to CMIP6. CERFACS and CNRS have been devoting each about 0.75 FET (Full Time Equivalent) to OASIS since 1991 and 2007 respectively, ensuring development, maintenance and user support of the coupler. Of course, temporary but important funding streams (e.g. PRISM, CICLE, METAFOR, IS-ENES1&2, ESIWACE) have complemented these stable resources. Currently both organisations commit to keep on supporting the coupler, especially

in the framework of CLIMERI-France the French national infrastructure for climate modelling recently set-up.

Regarding the XIOS I/O server, it has been recognised for a while that the main functions of I/O servers and couplers, i.e. communication and transformation of data, have much in common. The question of “convergence” between XIOS and OASIS therefore naturally arose and was deeply analysed in ESIWACE (see deliverable D2.5). This analysis leads to the conclusions that XIOS already contains theoretically most of the functionality required to act as a coupler but also that it is not fully developed, tested and validated yet. So even if it is too early yet to encourage the climate modelling community to switch to XIOS for coupling, the current plan is to extend XIOS communication so to support coupling between two components, and to propose in the mid-term this evolved tool as a unique tool for IO and coupling. In addition to temporary resources (IS-ENES2, ESIWACE, ICOMEX), XIOS benefits from about 0.5 FET by IPSL/LSCE. An additional full-time position for XIOS will be shortly defended as a high CLIMERI-France priority. A very positive aspect of the convergence would be to avoid duplication of development efforts and to gather the current OASIS and XIOS human resources around one single tool. This convergence would allow the long-term support of both coupler and I/O server tools for the climate community.

Work package 3 has focused on tackling the challenges that will face those deploying and building environments that do not only include the models but also manage the full workflow. Workloads need to cater for real-time operational and production activities as well as for research and development. Human efficiency is essential to exploit increasingly complex software, workflows and systems. The approach to sustainability in this work package has been to build on and enhance existing communities to further strengthen them. In open source environments, success leads to further investment.

For example, the Cylc workflow scheduler started at NiWA and then grew into a bi-lateral endeavour between NiWA and the Met Office. Adoption of Cylc across the Unified Model Partnership⁵ and Met Office academic collaborations has provided a very broadly based and challenging user community covering the full workflow for weather and climate. This has driven a user-centric development culture that has been accelerated by ESIWACE funding. This has led to both industry interest in Cylc and a widening developer base as can be seen from the recent Cylc development workshop held in Melbourne, Australia⁶ with 10 registered potential developers from 5 institutions including an industry partner - Altair. This secures, as far as is possible, a good future for self-sustaining Cylc development and the involvement of Altair brings a partner that has a clear commercial benefit in ensuring Cylc meets as wide a

⁵ <https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/research/collaboration/um-partnership>

⁶ <https://cylc.github.io/cylc-admin/dec-workshop-agenda>

requirement as possible in the HPC environment. Sustained community engagement through IS-ENES3 and ESiWACE2 is aimed at further encouraging user adoption through outreach targeted support and strategic investment for the future challenges of workflows that need to respond better to data locality.

The other example is Spack, a tool for the preparation and maintenance of a software environment. Spack⁷, a flexible software package manager, was chosen for the deployment and maintenance of the software packages related to ESM within the project because it was targeted at HPC and aims at a much wider community than our own. As with Cylc, the number of contributors to the code base of Spack has increased. In this case by a factor of 4 (more than 350 people worldwide currently) since that choice was made, which seems to prove the viability of the project in a long term. The interest shown by the ESM community in Spack and their recognition of it as a tool suitable to their needs – DKRZ is now considering to use Spack for their system configuration – ensure that the efforts put in the development of the package manager in the scope of ESiWACE will be supported further.

The key outputs from WP4 in ESiWACE will be the storage business model (already delivered), the ESiWACE Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) with some prototype backends, and the semantic storage library prototypes. Of these activities:

- The storage business model is already informing activities at both DKRZ and STFC, discussions are underway as to how to get it formally published in the literature.
- ESiWACE2 has specific goals to improve the ESDM and semantic storage layer so that they are easily and reliably deployable – at that point it will be much easier to make a sustainability case and investigate a business model.
- There are a number of components within the semantic storage layer, one of which is the Joint Data Migration App (JDMA)⁸ which provides a simple front end to data migration between disk, object store and tape. An early version of this tool, badged as the JASMIN Data Migration App, is due to go into production on JASMIN (<https://jasmin.ac.uk>) in 2019 (beta testing is underway). As a production activity within JASMIN, the maintenance of this tool will be underwritten by the JASMIN team at ESiWACE partner STFC, but the learning will feed into the ESiWACE functionality extensions. A key part of the longer-term sustainability of these packages will be growing and developing an open source community of users and developers, but it is helpful that a first version will be in production soon.

⁷ <https://spack.io>

⁸ https://cedadev.github.io/jdma_client/docs/build/html/jdma_client/intro.html

- d. *Investigation as to whether collaborative funding could be sought from existing and future downstream services and projects.*

This aspect has not been directly addressed within the ESiWACE project but was followed in the ExtremeEarth proposal which was coordinated by an ESiWACE partner with many contributions from the ESiWACE consortium.

- e. *Address “classical” funding schemes through the Joint Programming Initiative on Climate, national funding agencies or through subsequent calls of the European Commission.*

Since there was a call for a second round of Centers of Excellence (CoE) which explicitly solicited applications for a second phase of existing CoEs the consortium applied to this call. Through our governance structures in particular the HPC task force we evaluated and followed a number of other funding opportunities. For more details see chapter 5.

The Joint Programming Initiative on Climate (JPI Climate) gathers 17 European countries with the objectives to align national programs in support to the societal challenge of climate change. As part of its Action Group on “Next Generation Climate Science in Europe”, JPI Climate is concerned by scientific issues related to Earth’s climate system modelling such as climate predictability, climate extremes as well the development of the next generation Earth system models. As such, JPI Climate has endorsed the ExtremeEarth initiative. JPI Climate could then serve as a platform to further discuss common strategy on Earth’s climate system modelling.

4 Concrete Work foreseen in ESiWACE2

4.1 Sustaining ESiWACE achievements

The ESiWACE2 work plan is directly targeted to sustain the work done in ESiWACE with respect to extreme-scale computing and data handling. This is expressed by the main objectives which are to (1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021 and (2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available. There is a clear inherent sustainability path, starting from established Earth system models, including now the developments done for the ESiWACE demonstrators and leading to exascale-ready implementations of these models which can and will be used to address innovative science cases. The ESiWACE demonstrators will serve as a basis to push the resolution of production ready simulations with coupled very high resolution Earth system models. This will be secured through the commitment of the model owners to provide scientific guidance in configuring, and in testing and evaluating the models as in-kind contribution.

4.2 Sustainable Earth system model development

ESiWACE2 will establish, evaluate and watch new technologies for the community that have the potential to play a crucial role to port and run weather and climate models on exascale supercomputers in the future. This will build on previous developments from other projects, like the ESCAPE and ESCAPE-2 projects, but will also rely on commitments of the partners to invest in these technologies, in particular Domain-Specific Languages and Machine Learning methods. In particular ESiWACE2 will extend and support a new High Performance Climate and Weather benchmark which will prototypically be developed in ESCAPE-2.

4.3 Sustainable data handling tools

ESiWACE2 will provide the necessary tool chain to handle data at scale. It will take the components of Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) developed in ESiWACE, and make them more reliable, working with industry and the wider community to embed them into existing open-source/open-development packages which have their own sustainability trajectories. Industrial partners will build prototypes for appliances, which if successful, could have their own ongoing evolution funded by sales. The ESDM (and the packages into which it is embedded) will become integral to writing simulation data at exascale, providing incentives for ongoing investment. An additional activity within ESiWACE2 will exploit these tools to analyse and visualise data, adding further incentives for both partner institutions and the wider community to invest in the long-term maintenance and development of the entire toolchain.

4.4 Piloting community services

A new activity, led by a new partner which is not directly from the weather and climate community, the Netherlands eScience Center, together with industry partner Bull/ATOS, is the development and provision of services to groups in weather and climate modelling both within and outside of the ESiWACE2 consortium. The services will be provided to selected applicants on a peer review based mechanism and at this stage is free of charge and limited to the efforts funded through the ESiWACE2 project. Based on the experience from this offer, possible future developments will be identified and a concept to evolve the prototype service activities into a full-blown and sustained service for the weather and climate modelling community will be considered.

5 The changing landscape

Many of the key elements of the ESiWACE environment were outlined in the following figure which formed part of the ESiWACE2 bid.

Essentially there are seven important components:

- I. **[International Science Bodies]** Supranational bodies which set out grand scientific challenges, many of which depend not only upon HPC, but upon innovative and large-scale use of HPC.
- II. **[European and National Bodies]** Major European and National agencies with an environmental focus (many of whom are partners to ESIWACE, such as ECMWF) and existing networks such as the European Network for Earth system modelling (ENES).
- III. **[Scientific Community and Scientific Programmes]** The wider scientific community, and major programmes either extent or planned, an important one of which would be the ExtremeEarth activity discussed below.
- IV. **[Pan-national projects]** Pan national science and technology projects focussing on current science goals and preparing for the next generation. ESIWACE2 (and ESIWACE) have positioned themselves to address the challenges of exascale computing as they apply to elements of (but not all of) high-resolution weather and climate modelling. Other projects to be discussed below address other elements of exascale computing and weather and

climate science. (Not shown on the figure is the dependency that most pan-national projects have upon national support, whether from institutions, infrastructure, or other projects.

- V. **[HPC and Data Systems]** All of these projects are underpinned by HPC and data systems that themselves need to deliver robust and reliable services to support existing science, as well as evolve towards delivering on next generation computing aspirations such as exascale computing.
- VI. **[The European HPC Industry]** The European HPC industry is intimately related to this activity, and will necessarily become more intimately involved, as co-design becomes more crucial in the context of exascale deployments.
- VII. **[Downstream Users]** The consumers of these activities are assumed to be numerical weather prediction and climate services (such as Copernicus) which themselves feed products and services into society which address economic and environmental goals. The ESiWACE projects were not designed with direct engagement with weather and climate data users, whether the public or companies working in the field.

Not directly present on the diagram, but crucial to the environment are the major funders (in particular the various directorates of the European Commission and the various national funding agencies) and their strategic goals and aspirations. In the context of ESiWACE these play out mostly in terms of the project funding opportunities and in the support for industry and the HPC and data systems (essentially their directly support for categories IV, V, and VI).

This broad picture hasn't changed over the last decade, but the activity within each of these components has changed significantly. In particular, since the advent of ESiWACE, we can identify the following elements of change in these categories:

1. There are a set of updated World Climate Research Grand Challenges, and an even greater drive to address both weather and climate risk with higher-resolution modelling and large ensembles.
2. A growing recognition that institutions do not have the resources to "go it alone" – a greater desire for collaboration on next generation challenges. The ENES community strategy espoused by Mitchell et al.⁹ has been updated (Joussaume et al., 2018¹⁰) with more clarity about community goals and priorities.

⁹ [Mitchell J., Budich R., Joussaume S., Lawrence B. and Marotzke J. \(2012\), Infrastructure strategy for the European Earth System Modelling community 2012-2022, ENES Report Series 1, 33pp. <https://doi.org/10.5285/ca90b281d6ff4c9b99bbdeb5fa63f3>.](https://doi.org/10.5285/ca90b281d6ff4c9b99bbdeb5fa63f3)

3. Within Europe, the opportunity for large-scale collaborative science provided by the FET Flagship projects birthed the ExtremeEarth consortium – with over 120 letters of support from across society, industry and academia, a programme was devised which would enable a giant leap forward in simulating, and exploiting data related to the solid earth, natural hazards and climate change. Anticipating a fundamental redesign of workflows and the exploitation of a thousand-fold increase in computation, it would have required a new level of pan-national research and service integration, with a new operating and governance model. Unfortunately, it has not yet been funded, and while there will be renewed efforts to find funding, the ideas and concepts provide a context to establish a longer-term vision for the ESiWACE Centre of Excellence.
4. The ESiWACE consortium has worked closely with a range of other H2020 projects, and alongside ESiWACE2, a number of new projects have been funded which fit into the broad spectrum of activities needed to sustain the existing science programme (including, as expected, IS-ENES3) as well as those focused on other aspects of moving towards exascale (e.g. ESCAPE-2). ESiWACE partners have been involved in the inception of many of these projects, contributing use cases, requirements and fundamental strategic goals.
5. Some ESiWACE partners run large HPC and data systems, and there has been a close relationship between the ESiWACE community and PRACE. The advent of the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking and the roadmap to pre-exascale and on to exascale will provide opportunities, likely through both centralised European provision and hosting partners. ESiWACE partners have contributed to the system requirements of the pre-exascale systems and are likely to have the same role when it is time to focus on the exascale system designs.
6. The ESiWACE partnership already includes key elements of both the HPC and storage industry in Europe, but with the burgeoning range of hardware options, and the need for co-design to ensure the system architectures can meet our complex simulation and workflow requirements, it will be necessary to foster existing (and if necessary, establish new) close relationships with the wider HPC industry.
7. During ESiWACE and in the preparation of the ESiWACE2 and IS-ENES3 projects a clearer separation of concerns around downstream users has been established, with use of current generation of climate models for climate science and climate service

¹⁰ [Joussaume S., Lawrence B. and Guglielmo F. \(2017\), Update of the ENES infrastructure strategy 2012-2022, ENES Report Series 2, 20 pp.](#)

use cases (including developing and running CMIP-class models) being handled in IS-ENES3, and a tighter focus on next generation computing and the highest possible resolution global modelling within ESiWACE2. Those elements of the ESiWACE activity which were not directly relevant for the exascale focus (for example some workflow aspects) were moved to IS-ENES3. The institutional partners are focusing their supporting efforts accordingly. However, despite the separation of applications, it is recognised that many of the underlying activities have complementary sources of funding, and so a sustainable business plan has to address the entirety of the spectrum of activities, not just the component currently within the sphere of ESiWACE (and ESiWACE2) funding.

6 Next steps: Consolidating the sustainability plan

The primary goal of ESiWACE is to improve the ability of weather and climate applications to run on next generation computers. This involves optimisation of models, the development and incorporation of new software components and delivering on the complete workflow requirements from simulation through to analysis, visualisation and archive.

The ESiWACE description of the action has some built-in features to guarantee that the work will be of benefit for the community whichever funding futures transpire in. Although we asked for funding for a three years period, we planned for project duration of 48 months. The closing phase will see less directly funded work in the technical work packages, but governance and management will be continued by the coordinating entities. This phase will be used to transfer the support and service into a next phase, which as we now know is directly funded as ESiWACE2. Thus, the sustained support of the exascale relevant activities that started in ESiWACE is secured until 2023.

A key component of the coordination will be handled by the wider ENES governance bodies, and in particular the ENES HPC task force. The ENES HPC task force was established as an informal body by ENES many years ago, and it has operated since then with and without direct financial support. With the advent of ESiWACE, the membership was extended to include representatives of the NWP community and the scope was explicitly extended to the exascale. The task force is particularly active in helping to build project consortia, organising HPC workshops for the community and synchronising community response and requirements to European organisations like PRACE, EXDCI and Euro HPC. In the next few years it will have an element of direct financial support via complementary contributions to support key individuals from both ESiWACE2 and IS-ENES3.

ENES itself will be re-invigorated with a new set of goals, a new board, new institutional membership and an explicit scope that will cover all the infrastructure and technical (HPC and big data related) research and development requirements of the weather and climate community – at least where they require coordinated collaborative activities at the European scale. This work will be led out of the IS-ENES3 Sustainability work package, but by involving all the key players in the existing funded projects (and the weather and climate components of Extreme Earth) it will provide a venue for the development of an integrated and sustainable vision for the major activities, and with direct input from ESIWACE2, it will provide a vision for how the ESIWACE Centre of Excellence can remain distinct and sustainable into the future. It will address how some activities may be supported by a multitude of funding sources, from a re-focused national funding, to potential new collaborative instruments.

Although some of this work will be coordinated at the ENES level, the ESIWACE project will of course retain control over scope and aspiration of the CoE. The ESIWACE2 leadership team will exploit knowledge of other projects, and retain ownership of the ESIWACE business plan, which will become a formal ESIWACE2 deliverable, exploiting not only the context derived from ENES, but also expert knowledge of other relevant projects, and the Key Performance Indicators of ESIWACE2, measuring success and impact of its activities. We expect that, for this purpose, this activity will benefit from input through the activities of the Focus CoE (the EU funded coordination and support action for the Centres of Excellence) and result in a sound formal business plan.

As first steps towards the ENES oversight and the development of the ESIWACE2 deliverable we expect that during 2019 we will instigate a high-level inter-project discussion between the ESIWACE partners and the IS-ENES3 partners, where we revisit the separation of concerns and messaging around short term (project) goals and long term (sustainability) goals¹¹. At the same time, we expect IS-ENES3 to organise the re-scoping of the ENES board, leading to a future ENES “board activity” which will take input and consider some of the institutional aspects of these plans. The ESIWACE component of this will begin with breakouts at the upcoming joint ESIWACE General Assembly/ESIWACE2 kickoff meeting in March 2019.

We expect the community to continue to advocate and work towards an evolved version of the vision outlined in the ExtremeEarth proposal. ESIWACE will continue to take a lead in developing and scoping that work and ensuring that the core developments needed to take it forward are maintained with the ESIWACE framework until the time when a bigger effort can

¹¹ In particular, IS-ENES3 will organise a workshop in the 2nd half of 2019, targeting on the scientific, technical, legal and governmental aspects of long term sustainability of the various ENES infrastructure components. This will happen in close cooperation and with contribution of ESIWACE2.

be funded. To that end, the ESiWACE focus will remain on the largest problems, those for which exascale computing is necessary, and for which entirely new paradigms of working will be necessary, including re-evaluating how we use HPC in a future world where power constraints will make our existing workflows prohibitively expensive.

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